

Prepare RDM for Decentralized and Blockchain-Based Data Source

Wendy(Pengyin) Shan

University of Alberta Library, Canada
pshan@ualberta.ca

- Interactive Pages
 - Multi-Media

Web 2.0

Web 1.0

Static pages

Web 2.5

- Semantic Web
- Decentralization
- AR & VR
- AI

Web 3.0

- Rich interactions
- Large companies
- Mobile computing, clouding computing...

In a survey conducted by IBM in 2019

(<https://www.axios.com/2019/02/25/consumers-kind-a-sorta-care-about-their-data>)

81% concerned
Use of their data online

88% wanted
Clear policy for data usage in emerging technologies

But 71% could sacrifice
Privacy for technology benefits

Traditional data center will add decentralized feature to fit the new requests:

Future Centralized and Decentralized Data Mixed

Decentralized Data System - Solid Example

Should RDM join the certification process or create own app?

from <http://solid.georgetown.domains/technical-component>

miro

Blockchain-Based Data System - E-Book Transaction Chain Example

So, what could we do?

Possible Strategies

Decentralized Data

1. **'Whitelist' app, user and location**
2. **More metadata standard to improve security and integrity**
3. **International collaboration**

On-Chain Data

1. **'Transparent Transactions' for sensitive data transfer**
2. **Add guidance of encryption & decryption process**
3. **Governance on-chain and off-chain data**

One More Step: A RDM Chain?

for a multi-chain, data-capitalized future

RDM Chain - Basic Development Roadmap

Basic Idea

Distributed Ledger App for Encrypted Data Management

And more possibilities via smart contract...

Time to Brainstorm and Act

✓ Data Privacy Master

✓ Data Integrity Promoter

✓ Data Mining Expert

Future: More Interoperability

	Polkadot	Cosmos
Idea	Relay-Para Chain (Shards)	Hubs and Zones
Governance	Multicameral	Coin-Vote
Consensus	BABE & GRANDPA	Tendermint
Upgrade	No Hard Fork	Hard Fork Possible
Supporter	Web3 Foundation & Dr. Gavin Wood	Inter-chain Foundation (ICF)

THANK YOU!

Any questions?

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